

Advanced biological treatment of wastewater: A concise review

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ABSTRACT

Wastewater is a by-product of industrialization and urbanization processes. Developed countries generate more wastewater than developing and less developed countries. Even developed countries can't treat 100% of wastewater produced. This study was aimed to investigate advanced biological methods for wastewater treatment. It reveals that biological treatment is cost effective and eco-friendly. Microbes are the best arms to combat pollutants. Metabolic engineering of microbes is the advanced strategy to optimize wastewater treatment. New microbes and their potentiality must be investigated in future. Metabolic engineering in light of biofuel production utilizing wastewater as a resource must be explored massively in future.

1. Introduction

Wastewater generation is the indication of environmental pollution and is concerned with domestic, agricultural, aquacultural and industrial activities and is proportional to the use of fresh and drinking water. The economic development of a nation can't escape wastewater generation. Developed countries produce more wastewater than less developed and developing countries. Every country treats wastewater with effective technologies but no country can treat 100% of wastewater.

In houses and offices, water is discharged as grey, black and yellow water. Grey water contributes about 65% of domestic wastewater (Elizabeth et al. 2014). It includes sink, shower, bath, cloth washing, dish wash water. Grey water contains fewer pathogens and is safer to reuse (DeOreo et al. 2016). Black water is toilet water admixture of faeces, urine and anal cleansing water and contains numerous pathogens and contributes >25% of domestic wastewater in India. In India, yellow water i.e., urine generating from urinal

shares about 1-2% of domestic wastewater. It is free from pathogen and has a great fertilizer potential for agriculture and aquaculture (Jana et al. 2012).

Wastewater generation is an essential by-product of modern industries (Hangchang 2009). Industries like battery manufacturing, breweries, dairy, organic chemical manufacturing, pharmaceutical, electric power plant, food processing, iron and steel, mines and quarries, nuclear, petroleum refining and petrochemicals, pulp and paper, textile dyeing, leather, water treatment, wood preserving, wool processing etc. are the great source of wastewater. In India, approximately 6.2 billion liters of industrial wastewater is generated every day (Jain 2015). Interestingly, pulp and paper industries produce 201.4 MLD whereas food, dairy and beverage industries produce 6.5 MLD (Goel 2017). Industrial wastewater is highly toxic because numerous pollutants are released from industries in it (Table 1).

Table1 Industries and their pollutants released in water

Industries	Pollutants released	References
Battery manufacturing	Cd, Cr, Co, Cu, CN ⁻ , Fe, Pb,, Mn, Hg, Ni, Zn, Ag, oil and grease	EPA, 2017
Organic chemical manufacturing	benzene, chloroform, naphthalene, phenols, toluene, vinyl chloride, Cr, Cu, Pb, Zn, Ni etc.	Nasar et al, 2007; EPA, 1987
Electric power plant	Pb, Hg, Cd, Cr, As, Se, NO ₃ ⁻¹ , NO ₂ ⁻¹ etc.	EPA, 2015
Food industry	Organic matter, Pb, Cd, NO ₂ ⁻¹ and NO ₃ ⁻¹ .	Noukeu et al, 2016
Iron and Steel industry	NH ₃ , CN ⁻¹ , poly aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), Fe, Zn, Pb, Hg, Cd, Ni and F	Mirabile et al, 2008
Mines and quarries	Particles of rocks and minerals, hydraulic oils etc.	Tyulenev et al, 2017
Nuclear industry	³ H, ¹⁴ C, ⁸⁹ Sr, ⁹⁰ Sr, ⁵⁵ Fe and ⁶³ Ni	Ding et al, 2016
Petroleum refining and petrochemicals	NH ₃ , H ₂ S Napthenic acids Poly aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) Phenol	Atlas and Buyukgungor, 2008 Wang et al, 2015 Shokrollahzadeh et al, 2008 Abdelwahab et al, 2009
Pulp and paper industry	Organic matter, chlorinated dioxin and furans, dibenzofuran, dibenzo-para-dioxin, polychlorinated phenols etc.	Hubbe et al, 2016
Textile dyeing industry	Cl ⁻ , S ⁻² , OCl ⁻ , OH ⁻ and SO ₄ ⁻² Na, Cd, Cr, Cu, Fe, Pb, As, Hg, Ni and Zn Benzidine	Tholoana, 2007 Mostafa, 2015 Alves et al, 2007
Wood preserving plants	As, Cu, Cr, phenols, oil and grease.	EPA, 2018
Wool processing industries	As, Pb, Cd, Cr, Zn, Hg, Cu, S ⁻² and phenols	Singh and Jadav, 2014

Fig. 1 Percentage of municipal wastewater treatment in different high, middle and low-income countries during the years 2011-2012 (AQUASTAT 2014).

Agriculture wastewater is contaminated with fertilizer, pesticides, animal slurry, crop residues, antibiotics, vaccines, growth promoters and hormones (UNESCO 2017) and is not safe for domestic reuse without any treatment. Globally, 2.75 million km² of land are irrigated for agriculture (AQUASTAT 2014) and agriculture wastewater account for 32% of global

water withdrawal (4000 km³ year⁻¹ in 2010, AQUASTAT 2016) (UNESCO 2017). Simultaneously, these agricultural nitrates percolate through the soil and contaminate groundwater (Liu et al. 2017).

Industrial, agricultural and domestic water demand of a nation can be managed through the use of wastewater after

proper treatment. 180 countries out of 195 in the world treat wastewater (EPI 2018) by 0 – 100% (UNSD 2011). High-income countries treat about 70% of wastewater generation whereas upper middle-income countries treat about 38%, lower middle-income countries about 28% and low income-countries only about 8% (UNESCO 2017) (Fig. 1). Highly populated cities like Aqaba, Bangkok, Durban, Kampala and Manila have achieved 100% wastewater treatment and have honored “zero discharge” policy (IWA 2018).

Wastewater is treated in three subsequent steps - phase separation, removal of suspended and dissolved organic compounds and polishing applying about 15 techniques like – flocculation, coagulation, oxidation in aerated lagoon, oxidation in trickling filter, oxidation in activated sludge, ditch oxidation, pond oxidation, anaerobic sludge digestion etc. with waste removal efficiencies from 65 – 95%.

The objective of the study is to investigate on the advanced biological treatment of wastewater to enhance waste removal efficiency.

2. Composition of wastewater

Wastewater consists of 99.9% of water and 0.1% of solids. The composition of wastewater varies according to the primary use of water. Two major constituents of solid are organic and inorganic compounds. Carbohydrate, protein, fats, amino acids and volatile acids etc. come under the organic compounds while sodium, calcium, chlorine, potassium, sulphate, magnesium, bicarbonate, ammonium and heavy metals ions, etc. constitute inorganic part. Hydrocarbons, fats, oils, waxes and high molecular weight fatty acids are collectively referred to as oil and grease come under organic category (Hammer and Hammer 2001). Biological components include bacteria, fungi, virus and algae, etc. Eutrophication is a common phenomenon worldwide due to the discharge of industrial wastes into open water resources which includes vast amounts of nitrogen and phosphorous (Camejo et al. 2017).

3. Characteristics of wastewater from various industries

Wastewater characterisation depends upon changes in colour, odour, total dissolved solids (TDS), total suspended solids (TSS), pH, conductivity, temperature, biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), chemical oxygen demand (COD) and volatile organic compounds (VOCs), etc. Ansari et al. (2012) analyzed physical characteristics of distillery effluent samples and observed spent wash colour to be dark brown, odour unpleasant, total solids - 42400.2 ± 6.4 (CPCB: 90000-120000), total dissolve solids - 38200.2 ± 4.8 , total suspended solids - 4200.0 ± 0.0 , pH- 4.2 ± 1.2 (CPCB: 3.7-4.5), electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{mho/cm}$) - 16450.8 ± 8.2 , total hardness - 2432.4 ± 5.4 , calcium- 2070.0 ± 2.6 (CPCB: 2000-3500), magnesium - 2260.5 ± 6.7 , alkalinity - 2864.5 ± 8.0 , chloride - 8530.2 ± 8.3 (CPCB: 5000-6000), dissolve oxygen - Nil, biochemical oxygen demand - 32300.8 ± 10.8 (CPCB: 45000-50000), chemical oxygen demand - 57164.6 ± 12.9 (CPCB: 80000-100000), ammonicalnitrogen - 1254.4 ± 2.4 (CPCB: 1000-2000), total phosphorus - 44.4 ± 5.6 (CPCB: 200-300), total potassium - 7440.2 ± 3.8 (CPCB: 8000-12000). All values given here are in mg/litre.

4. Wastewater treatment

Wastewater treatment refers to the application of various treatment methods on wastewater to make it reusable or less harmful to the environment when discharged. Methods of treatment used for removal of contaminants using physical, chemical and biological reactions are known as unit operations and they are categorized as primary, secondary and tertiary treatment methods. Primary treatments involve physical operations such as screening and sedimentation for removal of floating and settleable solids found in wastewater. Secondary treatments involve chemical and biological processes to remove most of the organic and inorganic matters present in the wastewater. Then comes the tertiary treatment methods or advanced techniques. Treatment of wastewater must be designed specifically for the specific effluent produced.

Table 2 Various methods of biological treatment (Abdel-Rouuf et al. 2012 and Butler et al. 2017)

Process	Treatment Agents	Waste treated
Trickling filters (attached growth)	Packed bed covered by the microbial film	Acetaldehyde, benzene, chlorinated hydrocarbons, nylon, rocket fuel
Activated sludge (suspended growth)	Aerobic microorganisms suspended in wastewater	Refinery, petrochemical and biodegradable organic wastewaters
Aerated lagoon	Surface impoundment plus mechanical agitation	Biodegradable organic chemicals
Waste stab.ilization ponds	Shallow surface impoundments plus aeration to promote the growth of algae and bacteria and algae symbiosis	Biodegradable organic chemicals

Table 3 Microbial degradation of various organic pollutants in wastewater

Organic Pollutant	Microbes involved	References
Petroleum hydrocarbons	<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i> , <i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>Bacillus subtilis</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> sp., <i>Alcaligenes</i> sp., <i>Acinetobacter lwoffii</i> , <i>Flavobacterium</i> sp., <i>Micrococcus roseus</i> and <i>Corynebacterium</i> sp. <i>Cladosporium</i> sp., <i>Aspergillus</i> sp., <i>Penicillium</i> sp. and <i>Fusarium</i> sp.	Adebusoye et al, 2007 Steliga, 2012.
Pesticides, herbicides, like Aldrin, Dieldrin and organophosphates like Parathion and Malathion	<i>Zylerionxylestrix</i>	Dhir, 2013.
2, 4-D, 1,2,3-trichloropropane (TCP)	<i>Pseudomonas</i> , <i>Arthrobacter</i>	Khalil, 2003 ; Gong et al, 2017
Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT)	<i>Penicillium</i> , <i>Serratia marcescens</i>	Izcapa et al, 2009 ; Bidlan and Manonmani, 2002.
Kepone, piperonylic acid, Lignocellulosic wastes, Pentachlorophenol	<i>Pseudomonas</i>	Cheremisinoff, 1996.
Ethyl benzene Wastewater	<i>Nocardiatartaricans</i> <i>Calothrix</i> sp. <i>Lyngbya</i> sp. <i>Chlorella</i> sp., <i>Chlamydomonas renhardtii</i> , <i>Parachlorella kessleri-I</i> , <i>Nannochloropsis gaditana</i> <i>Scenedesmus</i> sp.	Cox and Goldsmith, 1979. Miranda et al, 2017. Bela and Mallinga 2015 Singh et al, 2017; Onay, 2018
Heavy metals like cadmium Chlorinated aromatic compounds Lignin from Paper mills	Genetically modified <i>E. coli</i> <i>Desulfomonile tiedjei</i> <i>Aspergillus</i> sp. <i>Pseudomonas</i> sp. <i>Arthrobacter</i> sp. <i>Xanthomonas</i> sp.	Almaguer et al, 2011 Ni et al, 1995 Barapatre and Jha, 2016 Costa et al, 2017 Li et al, 2009 Ojha and Markandeya, 2016

4.1 Biological treatments of wastewater

Biological treatments of wastewater facilitate the removal of all the settleable colloidal solids and degrade or reduce the present organic as well as inorganic matters. Microorganisms utilize wastewater as a nutrient source for growth and reproduction resulting in significant reduction of organic and inorganic loads. Mainly bacteria and algae or their symbiomes have been explored for wastewater remediation across the globe (Table 2 and 3).

4.2 Metabolic engineering to treat wastewater

Metabolic engineering of microorganisms optimizes waste utilization and wastewater remediation. Co-culture of *Chlorella vulgaris* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* optimizes the removal of PO₄-P, NO₃-N and NH₃-N from wastewater (Guerra-Renteria et al. 2019) (Fig. 2). Lananan et al. (2014) reported that culture of *Chlorella* with effective

microorganism is efficacious in removing of total phosphorus from domestic wastewater up to 99.15%.

Removal of lignin in black liquor from paper industry was enhanced upto 52.3% through the inoculation of lingo-cellulose degrading microorganisms - *Comamonas* and *Pandoraea* (bacteria) and *Aspergillus* sp. (fungus) in the activated sludge of the black liquor under highly alkaline condition (pH 10) (Zheng et al, 2013). In cooking wastewater, the biodegradation of the N-heterocyclic compounds pyridine and quinoline were augmented by using *Paracoccus* sp. BW001, *Shinellazoogloeoids*, *Pseudomonas* sp. BW 001 and *Pseudomonas* sp. BC 003 bacteria (Bai et al. 2010). The membrane-aerated biofilm reactor treatment of textile industry wastewater coupled with *Shewanella* sp. XB was efficient to remove an azo-dye - Acid Orange 7 by 98% (Wang et al, 2012). Xu et al (2015) used *Streptomyces* sp. QWE-35 in membrane biofilm reactor to increase the removal of naphthalene significantly from coal gasification plant wastewater.

Fig. 2 Schematic diagram of symbiotic association of *C. vulgaris* and *P. aeruginosa* for optimizing nutrient uptake from wastewater under photoheterotrophic condition. The units of the values are mmol g⁻¹ dw of microorganism

The genetically engineered microbial strain *Escherichia coli* JM109 (pGEX-AZR) with higher ability to decolorize Direct Blue 71 (DB 71) was also used in bioreactor to augment the treatment of textile wastewater (Jin et al. 2009). Insertion of mice metallothionein gene (pMt-Thio) into *Escherichia coli* enhanced significantly the biosorption efficiency of lead (II) and Cadmium (II) from wastewater (Almaguer-Cantú et al. 2011).

Banerjee et al. studied various aspects to increase the lipid accumulation in microalgae *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* and stressed on metabolic engineering associated with other factors to get the desired result (Banerjee et al. 2016). Growth of *Chlorella* sp. in wastewater under heterotrophic condition exhibits maximum biomass production coupled with high accumulation of lipid content within cell (Viswanath and Bux 2012). Research suggests that treatment of wastewater must be explicitly designed for the particular type of effluent produced.

5. Conclusion

The following propositions can be concluded from present review:

- Wastewater is generated from human activities and through natural processes.
- Biological treatments are easy, cost-effective and eco-friendly.
- Activated sludge is the source of all decomposing microbes.
- Metabolic engineering of microbes is the best and advanced strategy for wastewater treatment.
- New microbes must be explored in future.
- Wastewater must be treated as resource for biofuel production.

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